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TEACHER MENTAL HEALTH IN EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the mental health of early childhood education teachers in the public school system, articulating subjective, work-related, and institutional aspects. Based on a literature review and qualitative analysis, it identifies the impacts of working conditions on teachers; psychological distress and the inadequacy of care policies. Considering the central role of teachers in human and social development, understanding and promoting their mental health becomes essential to guaranteeing a quality and humanized education.

Keywords: Teacher mental health. Early childhood education. Working conditions. Psychological suffering.